

ANAEROBIC BIODEGRADATION OF BILGE WATER USING A COUPLED MICROBIAL ELECTROLYSIS CELL AND ANAEROBIC GRANULAR SLUDGE SYSTEM

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Abstract

The present study investigates the biodegradation of undiluted bilge water (BW) by anaerobic granular sludge (AGS) couple with and without microbial electrolysis. According to the experimental results, the AGS couple with microbial electrolysis cell after a period of acclimatization seemed to be able to biodegrade bilge water. CH₄ content reached 52% in just five days after the feeding of the AGS with 100% of bilge water and application of 1V using commercial iron electrodes compared to AGS and AGS with electrodes. Regarding chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal values as high as 70% were observed. Among different Volatile Fatty Acids (VFAs) normally detected during anaerobic treatment, acetic acid was the most abundant.

Key words: Bilge water; anaerobic granular sludge; iron electrodes; methane generation, microbial electrolysis

INTRODUCTION

BW are greasy wastewaters that include lubricating oil, cleaning diesel oil, oily sludge, spills from the engine room, water leaks from internal pipes, and seawater filtrations (McLaughlin et al., 2014). High COD concentrations (2 g L⁻¹) and salinity values (25 and 35 g L⁻¹) which inhibit severely the biological treatment have been reported in the literature. Additionally, organic pollutants such as benzene, 1,3-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-phenol, octadecanoic acid etc. which are difficult to be removed have been recently detected in bilge water (Vyrides et al., 2018).

The aim of this study was to examine the biodegradation of undiluted real bilge water during batch experiments using AGS as an inoculum and commercial iron electrodes to enhance the process. Two different external potentials were investigated as a strategy to increase CH₄ generation and COD removal. During a period of two months (60 days), biogas production, biogas composition, soluble COD and VFAs) concentration were monitored.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental protocols

AGS was collected from a full-scale Internal Circulation (IC) bioreactor treating dairy wastewater at pH 7.0–7.5. Before to be used as inoculum, it was sieved (1 mm), washed with distilled water and placed into a Duran bottle (1L). The bottle was closed with a rubber septum, flashed with CO₂ and placed in a shaking incubator (34°C, 1 week). Real BW was provided from a company (Ecofuel Ltd, Cyprus) which collects and treats this type of wastewater. Batch lab-scale experiments were conducted in 1L reactors (effective volume of 0.7L). Each reactor was fed with 50 g of AGS and BW in different concentrations (25%, 50%, 100%) for four consecutive batch cycles. The remained

volume was filled with basal media (Angelidaki et al., 2009). Reactors were sealed and the pH of the liquor was adjusted to 7.5. For creating anaerobic conditions, CO₂ was flushed inside (5 min). Afterwards, the reactors were placed at 34 °C for a period of two months. Totally three reactors (R) were run simultaneously as follows: R0 (without electrodes inside) and R1 (with electrodes inside but without potential application) were the controls while in R2 external potential of 1V was applied. Gas and liquid samples were taken over time in order to determine gas composition, COD removal and VFAs Throughout the experiments the output voltage in reactor R2 was also recorded every 5 minutes by a data acquisition system (Keithley 2700) connected to a computer.

Analytical techniques

Soluble COD was determined according to APHA (2005). The biogas volumes were regularly measured using a 50 ml glass syringe. Gas composition (H₂, O₂, N₂, CH₄, and CO₂ concentrations) was determined by withdrawing 1 ml from the headspace and analyzing it in a gas chromatographer equipped with thermal conductivity detector (GC-TCD) (Vyrides et al., 2018). VFAs (formic, acetic, propionic and butyric acid) were determined using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) at 210 nm (Vyrides and Stuckey, 2009). The current across the resistor (10 mΩ) in MEC-AGS and MEC were collected by an automatic data acquisition system (Keithley 2750, Tektronix, USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the results, after the first 15 days of the experiment (end of cycle A) the content of CH₄ did not exceed 30% in R2 and found to be about 1.6 times lower compared to controls (48.4%). However, on day 19, just three days after the start of cycle B (feeding with 50% BW), the content of CH₄ found to be as high as 62% (R2) and it was like the values detected in controls. This indicates that microbial electrolysis cell coupled with AGS after a period of acclimatization (here 15 days) was able to biodegrade the BW producing CH₄. The feeding of all reactors with 100% BW resulted in substantial CH₄ production only in microbial electrolysis cell coupled with AGS (R2) whereas AGS (R0) and AGS with electrodes (R1) shows minor gas generation. Specifically, in reactor R2 the content of the gas found to be 51% in just 5 days after the beginning of cycle D. The results demonstrated that the system of AGS couple with MFC at 1 V is a promising technique and can improve the biodegradation of a refractory wastewater such as bilge. Regarding COD removal of 60% was observed in R1 at 25% of BW similarly to R0 and R1 and it was increased to 70% when BW was doubled. Chromatographic analysis of liquid samples for the existence of VFAs, confirmed the presence of only three acids and their concentrations were found to be in decreasing order: acetic acid > propionic acid > valeric acid.

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